

Terminologies and FAIR Data

Applications and Usage Patterns of the Terminology Service

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Abstract

The TIB Terminology Service is a central point of contact that brings together distributed, managed terminologies from a variety of research areas. The service has a graphical user interface to support knowledge engineers and decision makers in their work on and with terminologies. On the other hand, the service provides an interface with rich functionalities to support the integration and use of terminologies in tools that support data management infrastructures components in the FAIRification of research data. This paper presents insights to the applications used and a selection of early-adopters actively utilizing the NFDI4ING Terminology Service API besides NFDI external adopters. While the TIB service provides access to a broad range of collections, from a diverse set of research domains, the NFDI4ING Terminology Service is a tailored service for the engineering sciences.

The first part of this contribution motivates the handling of standardized terminology in FAIR research data management. The second part presents an analysis of the most common usage of the Terminology Service in research data management infrastructures components. Finally, it gives a practical overview of the utilization of the service in a selection of the analyzed components. In the last part, we look first at NFDI4ING usage and then at its application outside the NFDI. The following infrastructures components are examples of the Terminology Service adopters:

- Coscine is the research data management platform for research projects provided by RWTH Aachen for NFDI4ING. It enables data FAIRification (including storage, detailed metadata and collaboration with participating researchers) and uses the Terminology Service for creating Application Profiles.
- The Open Research Knowledge Graph is used in NFDI4ING to structure research papers for easier discovery and comparison. The Terminology Service supports enrichment of the nodes of the knowledge graph with standardized terminology to provide further semantic information.
- KADI4MAT, partly developed in NFDI4ING, is an open-source virtual research environment for research data management across disciplines. It allows term identifiers in metadata, automatically retrieved from the Terminology Service.

- DaRUS, the research data repository of the University of Stuttgart, offers a secure place to manage, exchange and publish research data and code. The Terminology Service was integrated in the publication workflow to assign standardised keywords. Work is currently underway to integrate the service directly into DaRUS as a vocabulary server with an auto-completion function, initially for the DFGFO Topic Classification.
- Data Manager – Zentrum für Quantitative Biologie (QBiC). The Terminology Service is used in a life science data management platform in which researchers can maintain terms directly via a user interface. The Terminology Service is applied to search for and validate terms.
- The Vocabulary Development Support Tool is being developed as part of the SC4EU project. Semiconductor supply chains are complex. From the raw materials to the delivery of the finished products, a large number of very different industries are involved. The digital reference ontology is being developed for standardized communication between them. The tool uses the Terminology Service to integrate existing terms into the ontology.

Keywords: Semantic metadata, Terminologies, Ontology development

Resources

The material and resources (e.g. data, model, codes, documentation, videos) which underly, support or are closely related to your contribution deposited on a repository, please include a title, the respective DOI(s) and brief description. E.g.

- Terminology Service. <https://terminology.tib.eu/ts> “Software based service for ontology management”
- Coscine. <https://about.coscine.de/> “Research data management platform for research projects”
- ORKG. <https://orkg.org/> “Structures research papers for easy search and comparison.”
- Kadi4Mat. <https://kadi.iam.kit.edu/> “Kadi4Mat is an open-source platform for managing research data across disciplines”
- DaRUS. <https://darus.uni-stuttgart.de/> “DaRUS is the University of Stuttgart’s secure platform for managing, sharing, and publishing research data and code.”
- QBiC Data Manager. <https://zenodo.org/records/14982421> “Data management solution for the life sciences”

Author contributions

Felix Engel, Angelina Kraft, Giray Tuncay, Axel Klinger: Methodology, Conceptualisation

Felix Engel: Writing - original draft; Writing - review & editing

Angelina Kraft: Writing - review & editing

Competing interests

No conflict of interests.

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